

INDEX

No.	Title of the Paper	Author's Name	Page No.
1	Trends in Goa's Agricultural Growth And its Determinants: A Geographical Study	Dr. Prakash. R. Morakar	05
2	Comprehensive Cost + 50 Percent More: will Indian Farmer's Ever Get It?—A Study of Minimum Support Price	Dr. Dasharath Mehtry	14
3	The Effect of Climate Change on Agriculture in India	Malati Shankar Patgar & Dr. Shridhar Hadimani	20
4	Climate Change and Its Impact on Agricultural Productivity in India	Mr. Balaji Waghmare & Dr. M. V. Suryawanshi	27
5	Impact of Climate Change on Agriculture and Food Security in India	Dr. M. P. Manakari	33
6	A Delineation of Crop Diversification of Bawada Circle in Indapur Tahsil (Pune District)	Mr. S. B. Shinde	40
7	Impact of Educational Attainment on Per Hectare Yield of Sugarcane: A Case Study of Village Chavanwadi in Solapur District	Dr. Arjun H. Nanaware	45
8	Agro Tourism- A Business Model in India	Dr. T. N. Lokhande	51
9	A Study of Levels of Agricultural Productivity in Latur District, Maharashtra (India)	Dr. Mukesh Kulkarni	56
10	"Modern Technique of Water Conversion in Drought Prone Area and Agriculture Development - A Case Study in Sangola Tahsil of Solapur District. (M.S.)"	Prof. S.G. Patil & Dr. B. R. Phule	62
11	Spatio-Temporal Analysis of Fruit Farming Cultivation in Kolhapur District of Maharashtra	Anita Magadum & Dr. R. V. Hajare	71
12	A Geographical Study of Agricultural Development Levels in Indapur Tahsil : Pune District	Mulani Mahammad Sheklal	75
13	A Geographical Study of Agricultural Regionalization for Planning Improvement in Osmanabad District	Dr. Ganesh Jadhav	81
14	A Geographical Study An Importance of the Agro -Tourism Activities with Effect on Socio-Economic Development in Maharashtra	Prof. Jawahar Chaudhari	86
15	Role of Agro-Tourism in the Development of Farmers in Maharashtra	Dr. R.M. Khilare	93
16	Impact of Climatic Changes on Agriculture Development	Dr. Gautam Dalvi	98
17	A Study of Agricultural Problems in India	Dr. D. S. Harwalkar	107
18	Agricultural Land use Efficiency and Changes Therein in Lower Sina Basin	Dr. Arjun Nanaware & Amar Wakde	113
19	Impact of Climatic Changes on the Agriculture And Socio System	Dr. Chandrakant Kamble	118
20	Agri-Tourism as A Source of Earning Income for Farmers	Dr. Rahul Surve & Dr. C.V. Tate	122
21	Agricultural National Policies in India	Vijaya Gaikwad	130
22	Agro Tourism Centers in Solapur – An over Review	Mrs. Z.A. Nayab	134
23	Changing Fruit Agriculture with Climatic Regions in India	Prof. D.S. Gaikwad	139
24	Scope and opportunities of Agro-Tourism in India	Mr. Amol Shinde	147

25	Disappearance Changes of Traditional Agricultural Effect on Land-Cover Solapur District Dr. Nagnath Dhayagode	151
26	Flood and its Impact: A Geographical Study of Kerala District of India Dr.Raut Prakash Soudagar	155
27	A Geographical Analysis of Crop Concentration in Beed District (M.S.) Dr. Jaideep Solunke	159
28	Role of Agriculture in Regional Development and Associated Agricultural Problems in osmanabad District (Ms) Mr. Vaibhav Ingale	164
29	Impact of Agricultural Deveipment on Rural Settlements of Daund Taluka in Pune District, Maharashtra Dr. D.J. Durgade	171
30	Impact of Climatic Changes on Cropping Pattern of Solapur District Dr. Sangram Chavan	180
31	The Role of Technologies For Future of the Agriculture Development Dr. Bapu Raut	183
32	Zone wise Agriculture Land Transformation in Solapur City of Maharashtra Dr. D. S. Narayankar	187
33	A Geographical Study of Agro- Tourism in Maharashtra Mr. D. S. Kadam, Prof. M.S.Jadhav & Mr. V.C.Wardule	192
34	Impact of Climate Change on Crop Diversification in Donaj Village(Ms) Dr. D. N. Ligade & Dr. S. J. Awate	196
35	Regional Disparities Among Agriculture Development in Solapur District (MS): A Geographical Analysis Dr. Govindrao Todkari	202
36	Impact of Chemical Fertilizer on Agriculture Production: A Geographical Analysis of Solapur District Dr. V.K. Pukale	208
37	Attitude of Farmers Towards Utilization of Draught Bullock Power in Dry Land and Wet Land Farming Dr. S. G. Sontakke	214
38	Challenges of Agriculture and Government Schemes in Indian Dr. Sheela Rampure	218
39	Psycho-Social Condition of Indian Agriculture and Indian Farmers Dr. Bajrang Metil	223
40	New Trends in Agriculture Library and Information Science Miss. Sapnarani Ramteke	225
41	Geographical Study of Chemical Fertilisers Use In Agriculture of Osmanabad District Dr. R.V. Tatipamul	231
42	The Study of Meteorological Drought Due to Rainfall Variability in Latur District of Maharashtra State (India) Mr. Kishor Shinde & Dr. Parag Khadke	236
43	Library Resources in Information Center for Agriculture Mr. Rishi Gajbhiye	242
44	A Geographical Study of Rural Settlement Types and Factors Impact the Rural Settlements in Hingoli District Balaji Avhad	251
45	Geographical Study of Fruit Farming in Akkalkot Tahsil of Solapur District Dr. Ankush Shinde	255
46	Agriculture Landuse and Irrigation Facilities of Vinchur Village in South Solapur Tahsil : A Case Study Dr. H. L. Jadhav	259
47	Changes in Agricultural Land Use Pattern of Solapur District Dr. S.A.Nimbargi	263
48	Problems in Indian Agriculture Development Dr. Ramdas Madale	268
49	Problems and Prospects of Ground Water Resources in Pune District of Maharashtra Prof. A. K. Phalphe & Dr. R. S. Dhanushwar	271
50	Monsoon and Indian Climate: A Geographical Study Dr. Sachin Rajguru	276
51	Geographical Study of Major irrigation Project in Marathwada Region Dr. M. T. Musande	286

Impact of Climate Change on Crop Diversification in Donaj Village(Ms)

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Abstract:

Nowadays climate change is worldwide weather phenomena associated with an increase in global average temperature. It refers to changes into Earth's climate especially the gradual rise in temperature caused by high levels of Carbon dioxide and other gaseous. It is periodic modification of Earth's climate brought about as a result of changes in the atmosphere as well as interactions between atmosphere and various other geologic, chemical, biological, ecological and geographical within the Earth's system. This phenomena also related with agriculture. Climate change indicates the changing pattern of crops and its production. In Maharashtra, Solapur district has considered Sorghum Warehouse (Jowariche Kothar). Mangalwedha is one of major tahsil for Maldandi jowar (traditional crop-wan) production since few decades. But recent time this situation is turned out due to climate change and maximum people are trying to get fruit crops because of declining the groundwater level. Donaj region is one of the major part of this situation. Due to this situation the cropping patterns are diversified and the production of major crops are declined. The major food crops area declined in 2017 because of changing climatic condition. Major crops of this village covered by cash crops due to change of advanced agricultural technology.

Key words: Climate change, Crop Diversification, UNFCCC, IPCC, Volcanic eruption

Introduction:

Climate change is a significant long term change in the expected patterns of average weather of a specific region. It may be also refers to the statistical distribution of weather patterns when that change occurs for decades to millions of years. However, the official definition by the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) is that, "climate change is the change that can be attributed directly or indirectly to human activity that alters the composition of the global atmosphere and which is in addition to natural climate variability observed over comparable time periods". However, scientists often use the term for any change in the climate, whether arising naturally or from human causes. In particular, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) defines, "climate change as a change in the state of the climate that can be identified by changes in the mean, the variability of its properties and that persists for an extended period, typically decades or longer. Climate change is caused by various factors such as biotic processes, variation of solar radiation received by the Earth, Plate tectonics and volcanic eruptions. Impact of climate change on agriculture will be one of the major deciding factors influencing the future food security of mankind on the Earth surface. Agriculture is not only sensitive to climate change but also one of the major drivers for climate change. Crop diversification (shift) refers to the addition of new cropping systems to agricultural production.

Study Area:

Donaj is one of the important village in Mangalwedha taluka in Solapur district of Maharashtra state, India. It belongs to Desh of Pachim Maharashtra region. Donaj village is

bounded by 17O25'48.30" N to 17O28'34.30" N latitudes and 75O31'30" E to 75O34'40" E longitudes. It is located 59 km. from district head quarter of Solapur and 16 Km. from Mangalwedha. It is 499 meters above mean sea level. The total area of the village is 1962.57 hect. As per 2011 census the total population accounts 2953 in Donaj Village. West, South and North part of this village consist deep black soil and it contains good moisture. Climate of this village is hot and dry.

Due to deep black soil the major crops of this region were Jowar, Wheat, Cotton and Sugarcane in this region

Map No.1

Objectives:

The main objectives of study are

- To determine changing cropping pattern in study region during the period of 1991 to 2017.
- To identify the main causes of crop diversification in Donaj village.
- To analyze the trends and patterns of agricultural diversification in study region.

Database Methodology:

In order to determine the crop diversification to the study region, a multi-parametric datasets was used. The detail of the primary and secondary data used for this study are mentioned as follows.

Primary Data: SOI topographical Maps 47O/11, Village Map, Field Survey

Secondary Data: geology and geomorphology map which are need for spatial distribution of crops.

Software used: Q GIS 3.4 & ENVI

In order to identify the cropping pattern in Donaj Village the primary and secondary data are used. The collected toposheets of study area were scanned, registered and mosaicked using GIS software.

Discussion:

Donaj Village is one of the major part of Mangalwedha tahsil. This village has good network of road transportation. In this village Jowar, Wheat, Bajara, Sunflower, Cotton, Grape, Pomegranate, Onion, Gram, Safflower and Maize are the major crops. Food crops, cash crops, plantation and horticulture crops are unevenly distributed in this region. Food crops percent is decreased during the period of 1991 to 2017.

Crop diversification: Crop diversification is generally viewed as a shift from traditionally grown less remunerative crops to more remunerative crops. The crop shift (diversification) also takes place due to some government policies i.e. TMO give thrust on oilseeds production. Crop diversification and also the growing of large number of crops are practiced in rainfed lands to reduce the risk factor of crop failures due to drought. In Donaj village resource related factors (irrigation, rainfall and soil fertility), technology related factors (seeds, fertilizer and water technology), household related factors (food and fodder self sufficiency requirement and investment capacity), price related factors (output and input prices, trade policies and economic policies) and institutional and infrastructure related factors (farm size, tenancy arrangements, research, extension and marketing systems) are some factors which are responsible for crop diversification. These factors are inter related each other.

The temporal analysis of the changes in cropping pattern is observed both at the national, state and district level. For the purpose of the present study crop pattern changes at the village level are evaluated by considering the area share of crops. In 1991 and 2017 time have been selected so as to capture the major events and stages in evolution of agriculture which are to direct relevance to the purpose of this study.

Cropping Pattern 1991:

In 1991, Jowar was the major crop (19.69 percent) in Donaj village. In this village Northern, Western and Southern part is deep and black soil which is useful for Jowar, Wheat, Cotton, Sunflower and Safflower. So, this crops contribute above 50 percent in study region. There were no agricultural land of Grape and Pomegranate in 1991. Eastern part of this region contribute Pearl Millet, Gram and Groundnuts crops. Some part of this region also haphazered the area under vegetables, which also useful for farmers in daily life. Due to sustainable geographical condition the gross cropped area under various crops are very high.

Map No. 2

Cropping Pattern 2017:

Due to changing climatic condition, the all major food crops area declined and cash crops percent is increased. Grape, Sugarcane, Wheat and Pomegranate area is increased in study region. In 2017, the area under various crops decreased in this village. Sorghum area have 7.25 percent and wheat area contribute 12.69 percent. Excepting Wheat crops area, all major food crops area declined in this region during 1991 to 2017. Map No. 3 indicate the decreasing agricultural land

area in Donaj village. But main cause behind this is the depletion of of ground water level and the decrease the percent of rainfall in this region. But farmers also try to increase the land production capability using new advanced technologies. One of the major crops in this region is Grape cultivation and sunflower agriculture land. In Kharif season sorghum, cotton, maize crops determine the farmers hopes of crop production. Nowadays farmers also trying to use various types seeds for maximum production of crops in agricultural land.

Map No. 3

Temporal changes in percent of different crops (1991-2017):

Graph No. 1 shows the cropping pattern of Donaj village in 1991 and 2017. It simply indicates that the area under various crops are decreased and some area under crops are increased. The main cause behind this is the trend of farmers towards this and change climatic

Graph No. 1

Graph No. 2

condition in this region. Sorghum and Pearl millets land area is decreased around the 12.44 and 9.28 percent respectively. Kharif and rabi types of crops are taken in this region. The kharif crops means which crops sown in June and July month. In this seasons maize, bajara, jowar, cotton, sugarcane, pulses and groundnuts are major crops taken by farmers in this region. Rabi crops are also taken in this region which sown in October and November month. In this season wheat, sunflower, gram, onion and oil seeds are major crops taken by farmers in this region.

Grape, pomegranate, sugarcane and other crops are increased during the period of 1991 to 2017. These are major crops which highly increased but wheat is also increased but the percent is very low. Graph no.2 shows the details changing cropping pattern during the period of 1991 to 2017.

Conclusion:

This present study discusses the pattern of agricultural diversification. Though the share of agriculture in the overall economy has been decreasing. Changes in the percent of gross cropped area also suggest a move towards specialization. There has been a significant increase in the percent of area under fruits. In summing up, some of the silent points that emerged after comparing crop diversification in Donaj village are as under.

- The percent area under grape and pomegranate increase in some part of study region.
- Sugarcane is another major crops which area also increased during the study period (1991-2017).
- In other crops vegetables and horticulture crops are slightly increase in this region.
- The percent area under Sorghum, Pearl millets, sunflower, cotton, safflower, onion, maize and gram has started declining under resource stress.
- Farmers are using new agricultural technologies for increasing per hectare production in this field.
- Soil fertility of this region also decreasing due intensive use of fertilizers.
- The traditional agricultural development policies in this region have not been favorable to diversified agricultural growth.
- Farm size and soil fertility determine the decrease area under cash crops i.e. sugarcane in this region.

- The future direction of small farm diversification in this region would largely depend on the direction and effectiveness of government policy that could influence the creation of appropriate socio-economic environment for diversified farming through necessary technological, infrastructural, institutional and administrative changes.

References:

1. Acharya S.P., Basavaraja H., Kumar L.B., Mahajanashetti S.B., Bhat Anil RS (2011): "Crop diversification in Karnataka: An economic analysis". *Agric. Econ. Res. Rev.* 24, pp.351-357.
2. Das, Saudamini (2009): "Addressing Coastal Vulnerability at the Village Level: The Role of Socio-economic and Physical Factors". IEG Working Paper Series No.E/295/2009, Institute of Economic Growth, New Delhi.
3. Fraser, R.W. (1991): "Production risk, product complementarity and product diversification," *Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 43(1), pp. 103-107.
4. Gupta, R.P. and S.K. Tewari (1985): *Factors Affecting Crop Diversification: An Empirical Analysis*, *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, Vol. XL, No. 3, July-Sept, pp.304-305
5. Haque T. (1995) (ed): "Small Farm Diversification- Problems & Prospect", NCAP, New Delhi.
6. Jha B., A. Tripathy and B. Mohanty (2009): "Drivers of Agricultural Diversification in India", IEG Working Paper Series No.E/-2009, Institute of Economic Growth, New Delhi.
7. Jha, Brajesh (1996): "Farm-level Diversification: Some Disconcerting Evidences from the Green belt of India". *Agricultural Economics Research Review*, 9(1), pp. 49-56.
8. Jha, Brajesh. (1995): "Growth and Instability in Agriculture Associated with New Technology: District Level Evidences" *Agri. Situation in India*, 49 (7), pp. 517-524
9. Joshi P. K., A. Gulati and Ralph Cummings Jr. (2007) (ed): "Agricultural Diversification and Smallholders in South Asia", New Delhi: Academic Foundation.
10. Mali, N.G. and Ligade D.N. (2015): "The socio-economic status of livestock farmers: A micro level study of Donaj village in Mangalwedha tahsil of Solapur district (MS)". *Research Front.*, 3(3), pp. 21-26
11. Mohan R (2006): "Agricultural credit in India: status, issues, and future agenda". *Econ Polit Wkly* 41(11), pp. 1013-1023
12. Shiyani R.L. and H.R. Pandya (1998): "Diversification of Agriculture in Gujarat: A Spatio-temporal Analysis" *Indian Journal of Agri. Economics*, 53, (4), pp. 627-639.
13. Walker T.S., R. P. Singh and N. S. Jodha (1983): "Dimensions of Farm Level Diversification in the Semi-arid Tropics of Rural South India." *Economic Programme Progress Report 51*, ICRISAT, Hyderabad.